

**EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS
IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION**

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Abstract: The article analyzes the ways in which training using pedagogical skills and new teaching methods increases the quality of the educational process, increases the interest of students in science, and what are the tasks of the teacher in this.

Key words: Knowledge, teacher, pedagogical method, game technology.

In the educational process, modern educational technologies are used to improve the quality of education, to make effective use of study time, and to reduce the share of reproductive activity of students in order to realize the cognitive and creative activity of the student. Home work. Modern educational technologies are aimed at individualization, remoteness and variability of the learning process, academic mobility of students, regardless of age and level of education.

Based on the experience of using innovative methods in pedagogical activities, some of their advantages can be distinguished: they help students learn active methods of acquiring new knowledge; provide an opportunity to acquire a high level of personal social activity; creating conditions in which students do not learn during the educational process; encourage creative activity of students; helps to bring the study closer to everyday life practice, to form not only knowledge, skills and abilities in science, but also an active life position. At the current stage, education primarily focuses on the development of the individual, increasing his

activity and creative abilities, therefore, independent work of students, self-control, aimed at expanding the use of self-monitoring methods. active forms and methods of teaching, all this can be achieved only when there is interest in the learning of science by students. Cognitive interest is an intellectual and emotional reaction to the educational process, a student's desire to learn, to perform individual and general tasks, and interest in the activities of the teacher and other students.

Cognitive activation is a process of constant motivation for purposeful learning. A modern teacher should use various methods of activation, combining different forms, methods, teaching tools that stimulate the activity and independence of students, and introduce innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process. Graduates of secondary special vocational education institutions are subject to high requirements for admission to higher education institutions or employment. They must be able to adapt to the complex modern world: they need not only the acquired knowledge, but also the ability to find it themselves, to feel themselves as capable people in any field, and to think creatively in order to successfully establish themselves in life.

Some traditional teaching techniques and methods are one of the reasons for this loss of interest. In order to develop students' interest in learning science, it is necessary to use traditional methods of teaching, using methods that contribute to motivating students to practical and intellectual activities; formation and development of cognitive interests and abilities; development of creative thinking, as well as elements of innovative technologies (elements of problem-based, student-oriented education, information and communication technologies, etc.). The success of the lesson and the consistency of knowledge are directly proportional to the level of development of students' cognitive interest in science.

One of the important aspects of the lesson for the student is the understanding of the need for personal interest in learning, so that students can feel their competence not only in the result, but also during the entire learning process. the

impact of education on the development of the personality of the student. Therefore, a modern lesson should be built in a combination of specially organized activities and simple interpersonal relationships, so the lesson takes into account the age and psychological characteristics of students through a personal communication plan: their readiness to expand their scope. communication, sympathy for adult problems, desire for self-affirmation. Modern educational technologies help to achieve the set goals, for example: technology for differentiating the level of education; group technologies; computer learning technologies; gaming technologies; problem-based and exploratory learning technology; technologies of training intensification based on schematic and symbolic models of educational material; cooperative pedagogy.

Modern technologies make it possible to form and develop scientific and educational knowledge and skills, develop positive motivation for learning in the process of active multi-level cognitive activity of students in an emotionally comfortable environment. At the current stage, the concept of pedagogical technology is actively used in pedagogical practice. However, there are great differences in its understanding and application, and there are also many definitions given by different scientists, for example, BTLikhachev, VPBespalko, IPVolkov, VM understanding of pedagogical technology embodies the meanings of all definitions is a meaningful generalization. various authors. According to GKSelevko, the concept of "pedagogical technology" can be expressed in three aspects:

scientific: pedagogical technologies - the part of the science of pedagogy that studies and develops the goals, content and teaching methods and designs pedagogical processes;

procedural and descriptive: a description (algorithm) of the process, a set of goals, content, methods and tools to achieve the planned educational results;

procedurally effective: the implementation of the technological (pedagogical) process, the operation of all personal, instrumental and methodological pedagogical tools.

Thus, pedagogical technology functions as a science that studies the most reasonable methods of teaching, as a system of methods, principles and regulators used in teaching, and as a real educational process.

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